

erably up to 20 d. At 27 d, cumulative NH_3 volatilization was 4.8% of added ammonium chloride, 8.9% of urea +NBT, and 9.6% of urea.

NH_3 volatilization of ammonium chloride was half that of urea. Treating urea with NBT delayed ammonia volatilization about 7 d, but was ineffective thereafter.

The significant difference in ammonia volatilization loss between urea and ammonium chloride fertilizer was basically due to markedly lower floodwater pH in the ammonium chloride-treated soil (Fig. 2). Floodwater ammoniacal-N concentration was quite high in ammonium-chloride treated soil, indicating that ammonia gas concentration, not ammoniacal-N concentration, caused higher NH_3 volatilization loss in urea-treated soil. ■

2. Effect of urea and ammonium chloride on floodwater pH and NH_4^+ -N concentration, Ludhiana, India.

Crop management

Abscisic acid analog inhibits rice leafrolling caused by chilling

A. A. Flores-Nimedez and B. S. Vergara, *Agronomy, Plant Physiology, Agroecology Division, IRRI*; K. Doerffling, *Institut fuer Allgemeine Botanik, Universitaet Hamburg, Federal Republic of Germany*

One of the first symptoms of chilling injury to rice is leafrolling. This has been demonstrated to be due to water loss, and is correlated with leaf water potential.

We studied the effect of a new abscisic acid analog on leafrolling in response to chilling. Twelve-day-old seedlings of Samgangbyeon and 24-d-old seedlings of IR36 were sprayed with 10^{-4} and 10^{-3} , mol LAB 173711 per liter (abscisic acid analog developed by BASF, FRG) and a combination of LAB 173711 and tetcyclacis (a plant growth retardant). After 24 h, seedlings were transferred to a water tank for 3 d: Samgangbyeon seedlings for a root temperature of 11 °C for 7 d and IR36 for a root temperature of 5 °C. All seedlings were transferred to 29 °C for recovery.

Completely rolled leaves were counted and percent leafrolling calculated.

Leafrolling in Samgangbyeon and IR36 seedlings treated with abscisic acid analogs and chilled.

In Samgangbyeon seedlings submerged at 11 °C, treatment reduced leafrolling (see figure). It was only $\pm 2\%$ with LAB 173711 + tetcyclacis, about 30% with LAB 173711 alone, and 95% with no treatment. In IR36 seedlings submerged at 5 °C, leafrolling was minimized with ABA and LAB 173711 (only 4-10% rolling, compared with about 60% with no treatment). At 29 °C, rolled IR36 leaves reached 100% in the control and less than 40% in ABA- and LAB 173711-treated plants.

The effect may be due to the anti-transpirant activity of the analog: preventing water loss by transpiration and maintaining high internal water status for the plant system minimize or reduce leafrolling and, in turn, chilling injury. ■

Effect of nursery seeding density and seedlings/hill on late transplanted rice

H. P. Singh, *Narendra Deva University of Agriculture & Technology, P.O. Dabhasemar District, Faizabad 224133, U.P., India*

Although nursery seeding rates of 30, 40, and 50 kg/ha are recommended for small-medium-, and large-grain rices, respectively, farmers in many areas tend to sow at 60-80 kg/ha for weed control. In many rainfed rice areas, late rains also mean aged seedlings are transplanted.

We studied the effect of nursery seeding density and seedlings/hill on yields of late planted wet season rice. The trial was laid out in split-plot design with three replications. Soil was sandy loam (Typic Ustochrept) with pH 7.5 (1:2) and 0.58% organic C. Seedlings 40-45 d old were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing the last week of Jul.

Nursery seeding density and seedlings/hill did not affect yield. ■

Effect of nursery management on performance of inland valley swamp rice in Sierra Leone

I. Baggie, S. S. Monde, and A. B. Jalloh, *Rice Research Station, Rokupr, Sierra Leone*

We evaluated in 1988 wet season crop performance in an inland valley swamp of rice seedlings raised in the uplands. The soil was clay (Typic Tropaquept), with pH (water 1:1) 3.9, 6 kg Olsen's P/ha, 79 kg Olsen's K/ha, 3.2% organic C, and 0.12% total N.

ROK11 (130 d), ROK5 (145 d), and ROK10 (178 d) were planted at two seeding rates with two methods of sowing, and at two levels of fertilizer (see table). The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. The nursery was systematically laid out in an upland site. Seedling vigor and vigor index (seedling length [including root] × dry weight) were evaluated 27 d after seeding.

Seedlings were transplanted at two seedlings/hill, at 0.15- × 0.2-m spacing.